

A. What is vocabulary control?

Vocabulary control is a process by which we can generate, maintain and use controlled vocabulary. This process helps to store, search and classify data. Vocabulary control is understood as a way of ensuring that a particular set of words or phrases is consistently used within a given scope so that understanding or recalling them is simplified. This is often used to make information easy to locate in information retrieval systems, libraries, databases, indexing systems, etc. There are two stages of the search process through vocabulary control.

First step is to understand the needs of the users and analyse them to provide what they need.

The second step involves translation of the conceptual analysis to the vocabulary of the system.

Example

In a controlled vocabulary system, terms “car” and “automobile” would be regarded as one, allowing people who would query for either to obtain a similar result. In the same manner, broader or narrower terms may be linked with the aim of assisting users in finding related concepts.

B. What is the need of controlled vocabulary in IR?

There is a close relationship between Information Retrieval and Vocabulary Control.

- 1. A controlled vocabulary assists users in developing and improving search queries, appropriate terms and search process of users who are not experts in the subject in question.*
- 2. By using vocabulary control users can access relevant information in a short span of time very easily.*
- 3. In the retrieval process various users may use different synonyms or more common terms to refer to a given idea and concepts. For this reason vocabulary control is very useful for users.*
- 4. Understanding and analysing the users' need , vocabulary control helps to retrieve data for easy access.*
- 5. The differences in the terms that are used within indexing and that of information retrieval are reduced.*

C. What are the tools of vocabulary control?

Vocabulary control tools are very much important to access information easily. Below are some important vocabulary control tools:

1. *Thesauri.*
2. *Subject Heading Lists (e.g. LCSH- Library of Congress Subject Headings
SLSH- Sears List of Subject Headings)*
3. *Authority Files (e.g. LCNAF- Library of Congress Name Authority File)*
4. *Taxonomies.*
5. *Alphanumeric Classification Schemes (e.g., LCC, DDC, UDC)*
6. *Folksonomies*

D. What is classaurus?

Classaurus is a one type of vocabulary management tool, which is used for subject structure and indexing systems. Classaurus supports in organising the hierarchical and associative relationships of various terms used within the classification system. It is developed by Dr. Ganesh Bhattacharyya. It includes the essential features of alphabetical thesaurus. Classaurus can be designed either before starting indexing or along with the indexing.

*Classaurus has two parts - 1) **Systematic part** 2) **Alphabetical index part***

1. **Systematic part:-** *Systematic part includes common modifiers. Each entry in the Systematic part includes Descriptor, Definition, synonyms etc.*
2. **Alphabetical index part:-** *Alphabetical Index Part contains each and every term including synonyms occurring in the systematic part along with its address.*

E. What are the difference between natural language and artificial language?

1. *Natural language is free, has no limit to its vocabulary and it doesn't abide by any set of rules to describe.*
On the other hand, Artificial language follows several sets of rules and has certain limits.
2. *Natural language has gradually developed over time, social interaction, and trends in communication. It develops naturally as part of human culture.*
On the other hand, Artificial language has been developed with the help of natural language. Deliberately designed by individuals or groups for specific purposes. Changes only when it is updated by its creators or governing bodies.
3. *Natural language is highly flexible allowing for changes over time and across regions.*
Artificial language has limited flexibility depending on the domain.
4. *Natural language is human based language.*
Artificial language is Machine based language.
5. *Natural language can be both a primary and secondary source.*
Artificial language is always a secondary source.
6. *Natural language based on human vocabulary and grammar.*
Artificial language is based on databases and also vocabulary.
7. *It takes more time to translate natural language.*
On the other hand, it takes less time to translate an Artificial Language.
8. *Natural language is deduced from conclusion on the basis of observation.*
Whereas an Artificial Language is deduced from a certain definition.
9. *Natural language used by humans in everyday conversation, literature, media, and many other forms of expression. Primarily used for human communication in everyday life.*
Artificial language used in specialised fields, such as programming, linguistic experimentation. Created for a specific function such as communication between machines or certain human purposes.

Reference: -

- *Wikipedia-*
https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Controlled_vocabulary#:~:text=In%20library%20and%20information%20science%2C%20controlled%20vocabulary%20is%20a%20carefully,easily%20retrieved%20by%20a%20search.
- Svenonius, E. (2000). *The Intellectual Foundation of Information Organization*. MIT Press.
Description: Discusses the principles of information organization, including the role of controlled vocabularies and thesauri.
- Foskett, A. C. (1996). *The Subject Approach to Information*. 5th ed., Library Association Publishing.
Description: Focuses on subject analysis and vocabulary control in library science.
- Lancaster, F. W. (1986). "Vocabulary Control for Information Retrieval." *Annual Review of Information Science and Technology* 21: 17–42.
Description: An in-depth exploration of vocabulary control principles and their use in information retrieval systems.
- National Information Standards Organization. (2005). *Guidelines for the Construction, Format, and Management of Monolingual Controlled Vocabularies*. Bethesda, MD: NISO Press.
Description: A widely used standard on creating and maintaining controlled vocabularies.
- Library of Congress. (n.d.). *Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH)*. Available at: <https://id.loc.gov/authorities/subjects.html>
Description: Provides detailed insights into LCSH as a controlled vocabulary tool.
- Online Computer Library Center (OCLC). (n.d.). *FAST (Faceted Application of Subject Terminology)*. Available at: <https://www.oclc.org/research/themes/data-science/fast.html>
Description: Discusses controlled vocabulary adaptation for simplified indexing and retrieval.
- ISO 25964-1:2011. *Thesauri and Interoperability with Other Vocabularies – Part 1: Thesauri for Information Retrieval*.
Description: Defines best practices for creating and using controlled vocabularies like thesauri.
- ANSI/NISO Z39.19-2005. *Guidelines for the Construction, Format, and Management of Monolingual Controlled Vocabularies*. Bethesda, MD: NISO Press.
Description: Covers controlled vocabulary management and structure.
- Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). *Controlled Vocabulary*. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Controlled_vocabulary **Description:** A general introduction to controlled vocabularies and their application in various domains.
- Bhattacharyya, G. (n.d.). *Classaurus: A Vocabulary Management Tool for Subject Structure and Indexing Systems*. Unpublished manuscript.
- Chomsky, N. (1957). *Syntactic Structures*. Mouton.
Description: Explores the structure of natural and artificial languages, foundational to understanding formal languages.
- Allen, J. (1995). *Natural Language Understanding*. Pearson.
Description: Discusses the principles of natural language and its processing in computational systems.

- Sebesta, R. W. (2011). *Concepts of Programming Languages*. 10th ed. Pearson.
Description: Explains the features of artificial (programming) languages compared to natural language.
- Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). Natural Language. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Natural_language.
Description: Provides an overview of natural language characteristics.
- Wikipedia contributors. (n.d.). Artificial Language. Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Constructed_language.
Description: Discusses artificial or constructed languages, including programming and experimental linguistic languages.
- Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy. (n.d.). *Formal and Natural Languages*. Retrieved from <https://plato.stanford.edu/>.
Description: Discusses differences between natural and artificial/formal languages in logic and linguistics.
- ISO 639-1:2002. *Codes for the Representation of Names of Languages*. International Organization for Standardization.
Description: Covers standardization for natural and constructed language codes.
- Manning, C. D., & Schütze, H. (1999). *Foundations of Statistical Natural Language Processing*. MIT Press.
Description: Explores the intersection of natural and artificial languages in computational systems.
- **Bates, M. J.** (1989). *The Design of Browsing and Berrypicking Techniques for the Online Search Interface*. *Online Information Review*, 13(5), 407-424.

Description: This article explains how controlled vocabulary helps in the retrieval process, especially with the use of browsing techniques.
- **Salton, G.** (1989). *Automatic Text Processing: The Transformation, Analysis, and Retrieval of Information by Computer*. Addison-Wesley.
Description: This book covers information retrieval techniques, including the importance of controlled vocabularies in improving search results.